

In situ cross-linked chitosan hydrogels via Michael addition reaction based on water-soluble thiol-maleimide precursors

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ABSTRACT

Thiol modified chitosan (CsSH) was covalently cross-linked with a water-soluble bismaleimide (BMI) to obtain chitosan-based hydrogels by thiol-Michael addition reaction at physiological conditions. By modifying the composition of the as-prepared hydrogels, final properties could be modulated. Thus, the rheological and swelling behaviour were controlled by altering the amount of cross-linking agent in the networks. An increase in the cross-linker ratio led to an increase in the hydrogel storage modulus and decrease in swelling ratio due to provided rigidity to the structure and a higher cross-linked degree. Furthermore, 3D porous structures were observed to be sensitive to pH stimulus and showed interesting degradation kinetics under specific enzymes, suggesting the formation of these novel materials to be worthy of biomedical applications.

1. Introduction

Polymer-based cross-linked hydrophilic 3D networks can be considered as the future biomaterials for regenerative medicine [1], which involves medical approaches to improve, restore or replace biological functions of damaged tissues and organs, using cells, physico-chemical factors and/or engineered scaffolds [2]. Their highly hydrophilic nature and matrix complexation can provide structural integrity to tissue constructions, drug control and protein delivery to tissues and cultures, and serve as adhesives or barriers between tissue and material surfaces [3] since they resemble to the extracellular matrix (ECM). Thus, in recent years, *in situ* forming biomaterials from natural sources have been widely investigated as artificial 3D scaffolds given their excellent properties [2, 4–9].

Selective and rapid chemical reaction under physiological conditions is indispensable for *in situ* formation of hydrogels. Michael addition reaction, a highly regioselective and efficient 'click' reaction, holds great potential to address these challenges [10], and, hence, it has recently gained increased attention as a polymer synthesis strategy for tailored macromolecular architectures. The reaction proceeds rapidly at human body temperature under mild reaction conditions, in biologically friendly solvents including water, with no heat or light needed and displaying high conversions and favourable reaction rates [11]. The Michael addition chemistry involves the addition of a nucleophile to an electrophilic carbon-carbon double bond. In a typical Michael addition reaction, the nucleophile (known as the Michael donor) is added to the electron deficient carbon-carbon double bond (known as the Michael acceptor) to create a new carbon-carbon single bond [12]. Among this specific chemistry, thiol-click reaction holds great potential and it is widely applied in new compounds synthesis and hydrogel formation [13–16]. Although most of the research on thiol-Michael reaction is focused on the addition of thiol groups to acrylic compounds [10–12, 17–20], many other groups

such as vinyl sulfones, maleimides, fumarates, crotonate, ynones or propiolates can also act as Michael acceptors [16,21,22]. Moreover, it is of common knowledge the reduced reactivity of acrylates compared to maleimides [16,22,23], which can be reflected on the high number of research works dedicated to the thiol–maleimide reaction for the formation of hydrogels in recent years [23–31]. Maleimide is a biocompatible chemical compound that contains an unsaturated imide. In greater depth, bismaleimides, composed of two maleimide end groups, are attached through the nitrogen atoms via a linker, and are often used as flexible linking agents in polymer ‘click’ reactions [29, 32–35]. Thereby, thiol groups attack the double bonds of the maleimide moieties in thiol–Michael addition to generate a covalent and durable thioether bond [29].

Chitosan is an alternating copolymer of 2–acetamido–2–deoxy– β –D–glucopyranose and 2–amino–2–deoxy–D–glucopyranose derived from naturally occurring chitin. Even if chitosan is an interesting biomacromolecule that can form covalently cross–linked networks with excellent final features, it is non–soluble in water due to its rigid crystalline structure, which is the result of the inter– and intra–molecular hydrogen bonds [36]. Chemical modification of chitosan, through its reactive amino groups, has been shown to be a promising method for the generation of new functional materials, which would not change the fundamental backbone of neat chitosan, maintaining the original physico–chemical and biochemical properties of the polymer [37]. Nevertheless, the nature of the attached group could bring new properties into the original chitosan, i.e., the incorporation of thiol containing compounds contributes to solve the impediment of water solubility, since –SH groups are highly hydrophilic [38, 39]. In previously reported investigations, different thiolated chitosan derivatives, that exhibit good solubility in water were synthesized by amide coupling [36, 40–46] being of prime interest to generate novel biomaterials.

Accordingly, based on the extensive investigation on the thiol–maleimide linkage during the last decade, which has been previously mentioned, unique materials have been synthesized and widely studied in the present work. Accordingly, *in situ* cross–linked hydrogels formed under physiological conditions by Michael type addition between thiol–modified chitosan and poly(propylene oxide)–poly(ethylene oxide)–poly(propylene oxide) (PPO–PEO–PPO) based bismaleimide were prepared, being unknown until the date research focused on the formation of hydrogels from these singular tailored precursors. As the effectiveness of the cross–linking was proved to be influenced by the thiol/maleimide ratio, different cross–linker amounts were used in order to analyse its influence on the properties of the ensuing materials. The covalently cross–linked networks presented notably different properties in terms of swelling capacity and viscoelastic properties, depending on the cross–linking degree. Besides, based on the rheological study, the microstructural parameters of the polymeric networks were calculated. The efficiency of the reaction along with the favourable conditions evidenced the formation of tailored materials with propitious characteristics for their use in tissue engineering.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Chemicals

The following chemicals were used as received: chitosan (Cs, Sigma–Aldrich, medium molecular weight), thiolactic acid (TLA, Sigma–Aldrich, 95%), N–hydroxysuccinimide (NHS, Sigma–Aldrich, 98%), N–(3–dimethylaminopropyl)–N′–ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC, Sigma–Aldrich, ≥99%), Jeffamine® ED 900 polyetheramine (Huntsman, 900 g/mol average molar mass), acetic anhydride (PanReac), sodium acetate trihydrate (Sigma–Aldrich, ≥99%), triethylamine (PanReac), phosphate

buffered saline tablets (PBS, PanReac, pH = 7.4), glacial acetic acid (PanReac), sodium hydroxide solution (1 M), hydrochloric acid solution (PanReac, 37%), chloroform (Lab Scan Analytical Sciences), acetone (Oppac S.A.) and ethanol (Scharlau, 96 % v/v, extra pure). Deuterium oxide (Merck, deuteration degree 99.96%) was used for ^1H NMR analysis and deionized water was employed as solvent.

The average molar mass of the chitosan batch used in this study, estimated using an automated capillary viscometer, was 680 kDa. The degree of deacetylation (DD) was determined by nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (^1H NMR) following the same procedure of our previous work [37] and found to be 77%.

2.2. Synthesis methods

2.2.1. Synthesis of thiol-modified chitosan (CsSH)

Thiol functionalization of chitosan (CsSH) was achieved by amide coupling conjugation with thiolactic acid, following a reported procedure that has been consequently modified (Scheme 1) [47]. In brief, chitosan was dissolved in 2% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid to a final concentration of 0.5 % (w/v). Thiolactic acid, EDC and NHS were added to the solution while adjusting the pH to 5–6 using 1 M NaOH, and the mixture was stirred overnight in dark at room temperature. The pH of the surrounding medium will influence on the concentration of thiolate anions [48] and therefore, in order to avoid the formation of disulphide bonds (–S–S–) between the polymeric chains the synthesis was performed at pH 5–6. At that pH, the amount of the reactive form for the oxidation of thiol groups is low and the formation of disulfide bonds can be minimized [39,49]. The molar ratio of amine-to-carboxylic acid was kept at 1:1 and the thiolactic acid was activated with EDC and NHS in 1:1 and 1:1.1 molar ratios, respectively. The product was dialyzed in tubings of cellulose membranes (molecular weight cut-off of 12–14

kDa) for 3 days against 5mM HCl, then once against the same medium but containing 1% NaCl to reduce the ionic interactions between the cationic polymer and the anionic sulfhydryl groups, and, finally, once against 5mM HCl for 2 days. The dialysis process was done in dark at 4 °C for avoiding the oxidation of sulfhydryl groups [49]. Samples were lyophilized (yield: 88 % (w/w)) and stored at 4 °C in dark until needed for further use.

Scheme 1. Synthetic pathway for the formation of thiolated chitosan (CsSH).

2.2.2. Hydrogel formation through Michael addition reaction

In situ formed hydrogels were prepared by the cross-linking of thiolated chitosan (Scheme 2) with a water-soluble bismaleimide (BMI), which was synthesized by the modification of Jeffamine® ED 900 following two-step procedure according to our previously reported procedure [35]. BMI and CsSH derivative were mixed in PBS buffer solution (pH = 7.4) at different equivalent ratios of 1:2 and 1:3 thiol-to-maleimide in 0.7 mL total volume and allowed to gel at 37 °C for 2h to ensure complete conjugation [24]. Maleimide groups were added in excess in all cases to avoid the formation of disulfide bonds between thiol groups as far as possible. All hydrogels were formed at a polymer concentration of 7 % (w/v). Hydrogels will be referred hereafter as shown in Table 1.

Scheme 2. Hydrogels formation after the cross-linking via Michael addition reaction.

Table 1

Composition of the different hydrogel formulations (thiol-to-maleimide).

Hydrogel sample	Equivalent ratio (amine-to-carboxylic acid)	Equivalent ratio (thiol-to-maleimide)	CsSH/BMI (w/w)
CsSH/BMI 1:2	1:1	1:2	43/57
CsSH/BMI 1:3	1:1	1:3	34/66

2.3. Methods

The extent of amine substitution was quantitatively determined by reaction with ninhydrin in a modified way as described previously by Mahmood et al. [50] using a UV-3600/3100 from Shimadzu spectroscopy and the mathematical model proposed by Shitrit and Bianco-Peled was followed for the determination of the results [47]. Thus, in order to quantify the thiolation degree, ninhydrin reagent was reacted with the primary free amino groups of chitosan to form a coloured reaction product that show an absorbance signal at 570 nm. From starting solution of Cs and CsSH at a concentration of 0.15 % (w/v) in a mixture of 2 % (v/v) acetic acid, 1 % (w/v) acetic acid/acetate buffer (pH 5.5) and ninhydrin reagent solution (ACS Reagent, Sigma Aldrich), a set of solutions at different concentrations (0.1 – 0.03 mg/mL) was prepared. The final mixtures were incubated at 100 °C for 20 min. Samples were cooled down in an ice bath and the absorbance was measured. The degree of modification (DS) was determined via Eq. (1), taking into account the slope (m) of absorption vs. concentration curves which was empirically found to be proportional to the percentage of free amino groups.

$$DS(\%) = \left(1 - \frac{m_{CsSH}}{m_{Cs}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

where m_{CsSH} is the value of the slope of the modified polymer curve and m_{Cs} is the value of the slope of the neat polymer curve.

The amount of thiol groups immobilized on CsSH was also quantified photometrically by Ellman's test. In brief, 250 μ L of 0.1 % (w/v) CsSH in 1mM EDTA/0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer (pH 8) were reacted with 50 μ L of Ellman's buffer (0.4 % (w/v)) and mixed to a final volume of 2.8 mL. After an incubation of 4 hours at room temperature in dark, the absorbance of the sample was measured at 420 nm (UV-3600/3100 from Shimadzu spectroscopy). The amount of immobilized thiol moieties was calculated using a standard curve obtained from an increasing concentration of thiolactic acid.

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded on a Nicolet Nexus spectrophotometer at room temperature. Samples spectra were collected with a Specac MKII Golden Gate accessory equipped with a diamond crystal at a nominal incident angle of 45° and ZnSe lens, in the range from 4000 to 600 cm^{-1} , with 4 cm^{-1} resolution and 34 scans.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were collected by using PHILIPS X'Pert Pro automatic diffractometer operating at 40 KV and 40 mA, in theta-theta configuration secondary monochromator with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm) and a PIXcel solid state detector. The diffractograms were collected in the region $2\theta = 5^{\circ}$ – 80° , where θ is the angle of incidence of the X-ray beam on the sample. The crystallinity index of chitosan was calculated using the following equation:

$$CI^{XRD} = \frac{I_{110} - I_{am}}{I_{110}} \quad (2)$$

where I_{110} is the maximum intensity (arbitrary units) of the diffraction (at 110 lattices) at $2\theta \approx 20^\circ$ and I_{am} is the intensity of the amorphous diffraction at $2\theta \approx 16^\circ$ [51].

Thermal stability of the samples was studied by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a Mettler–Toledo TGA–SDTA 851 analyser. Samples of ~5 mg were submitted to a 10 °C/min heating rate from 25 to 800 °C under a dry nitrogen atmosphere.

The gelation time was determined by dynamic oscillatory rheology measurements performed in a Haake Viscotester IQ (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Spain) using the parallel plate geometry (titanium upper plate of 35 mm and steel lower plate of 60 mm) at 37 °C. The viscometer was equipped with a Peltier system for the temperature control and a solvent trap. The evolution of storage (G') and loss (G'') modulus was measured at in the linear viscoelastic region, at a constant shear strain (1 %, as it was determined by previous stress sweep experiments) and at 1 Hz.

The storage modulus (G'), loss modulus (G'') and the loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) of the final hydrogels were calculated by oscillatory rheometry using a Rheometric Scientific Advanced Rheometric Expansion System (ARES) and parallel plate geometry (diameter 25 mm) as described, in oscillation mode at 37 °C. After determination of the linear viscoelastic region (LVR) from stress sweep study, frequency sweep analysis was evaluated from 0.1 to 500 rad/s at a fixed strain of 10 %. In each case, the dynamic rheological properties of at least three replicates were evaluated.

The morphology of the as-prepared hydrogels was analysed using Hitachi S–2700 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) at 15 kV accelerating voltage, after placing freeze-dried samples on a SEM disk and sputter-coated with a 8 nm Pt/Au layer to reduce electron charging effects.

Swelling capacity (SR) of freeze-dried hydrogels was studied by a general gravimetric method. Samples were immersed in different medium (PBS and HCl 0.1 M) at 37 °C and at selected time interval, the swollen samples were removed, weighed once the excess of liquid was withdrawn with filter paper and again freeze-dried. The equilibrium swelling was considered to be achieved when the weight of the hydrogels no longer increased. The swelling ratio (SR) was calculated using the following Eq. (3).

$$SR(\%) = \left(\frac{W_s - W_d}{W_d} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

where W_s and W_d are the weight of the swollen and final freeze-dried hydrogel samples, respectively. The assay was conducted in triplicate.

Degradation studies of original chitosan and hydrogels were carried out by gravimetric analysis. Dried samples were weighted (W_0) and immersed in phosphate-buffered saline solution (PBS, pH 7.4) with 1 mg/mL lysozyme (≥ 40000 units/mg protein from chicken egg white, Sigma Aldrich) at 37°C. Samples were removed at fixed time intervals and washed out with deionized water to eliminate any superficial buffer and lysozyme traces. They were finally dried and weighed until constant value (W_t). Hydrolytic degradation was also studied as the control reference by incubation in lysozyme-free PBS at the same conditions. The measurements were performed in triplicate and the weight loss of the samples was calculated using Eq. (4).

$$\text{Degradation}(\%) = \left(\frac{W_0 - W_t}{W_0} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of CsSH derivative

The thiol functionalization of the chitosan was confirmed by the determination of the amine substitution degree (DS). Indeed, the ninhydrin assay, Eq. (1) was used to determine the remaining free amine groups of the thiolated chitosan derivative calculating the DS value of 26%. Moreover, the amount of thiol groups determined by Ellman's test was found to be 2162 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ of polymer. The amount of thiol immobilized in native chitosan was enough to avoid the insolubility problems and was found to be highly adequate for the subsequent cross-linking reaction. Moreover, higher molar ratios of amine-to-carboxylic acid groups did not provide better substitution yields.

FTIR spectroscopy was used for the comparison of the chemical structures before and after the functionalization of chitosan. Fig. 1 illustrates the FTIR spectra of both neat chitosan and thiol modified chitosan. Four common bands, belonging to the saccharide structure, at 1150, 1065, 1021 and 897 cm^{-1} could be identified in the two spectra [52,53]. Although the characteristics bands of the polysaccharide main chain remained unchanged in the chitosan derivative, significant differences were observed by comparing both spectra due to the polymer functionalization. The spectrum of unmodified chitosan (Fig. 1A) shows a strong broad absorption band with two peaks at 3357 and 3288 cm^{-1} , which were assigned to the stretching vibration of O-H and the extension vibration of N-H, respectively [54]. Besides, the band at 2873 cm^{-1} was attributed to C-H stretching vibrations of hydrocarbons. Besides, the amide I and II bands appeared at 1651 and 1584 cm^{-1} , respectively. The differences observed by comparing both spectra were due to the grafting of thiol groups into the chitosan chain via amine reaction. As it could be observed, in the spectrum of the CsSH derivative (Fig. 1B), the characteristic double peak of the NH_2 group disappeared and a single peak around 3294 cm^{-1} appeared, supporting the fact that the NH_2 group reacted with the

thiolactic acid [54,51]. Moreover, the functionalization led to the insertion of new C–H linkages in the polymeric structure, resulting in the differentiation of two bands at 2920 and 2851 cm^{-1} , which correspond to stretching vibrations of CH_3 and CH_2 , respectively [55], and the appearance of a new band at 1458 cm^{-1} [52,56]. Besides, amide I and II bands appeared slightly displaced in the CsSH derivative (1628 and 1518 cm^{-1} , respectively), which could be related to the addition of a new group after the amide bond formation [52,57]. Furthermore, the intensity of the band assigned to the amide II of the chitosan, which is associated to the C–N stretching vibration, was significantly stronger, suggesting that the grafting occurred at the chitosan amine site [56]. In fact, the thiolation of chitosan was also qualitatively confirmed by the appearance of some other new bands as the signal of sulfur–based groups at 796 cm^{-1} (S–C) and the characteristic band of the carbonyl groups (C=O) of the grafted thiol ended molecule at 1742 cm^{-1} confirming the success of the modification [52].

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of A) chitosan (Cs) and B) thiol–functionalized chitosan (CsSH).

The effect of the functionalization on the crystalline structure of the chitosan was evaluated by XRD. The XRD patterns of both samples are shown in Fig. 2. Chitosan exhibited its three characteristic peaks at $2\theta = 10.18^\circ$, 15.29° and 20.08° and the crystallinity index was calculated to be of 0.68 after applying Eq. (1). In agreement with previous reports,

the strongest peak at $2\theta = 20.0^\circ$ is assigned to crystal forms II, whereas the peak at $2\theta = 10.3^\circ$ corresponds to crystal forms I [40,45,58]. As expected, after the functionalization process, the degree of crystallinity dramatically decreased. The most intense peak was observed to be displaced but the almost disappearance of the signals could be indicating the existence of new intermolecular interactions that destroyed the regularity of the chitosan ordered structure [40,41,59]. The amorphous form of the chitosan derivative could present certain advantages for being used in biomedical applications [60,61]. Indeed, the showed water solubility of the CsSH derivative was likely attributed to the new stable amorphous form, enhancing both drug release capacity and subsequent absorption and bioavailability [62] and also the biodegradability and mucoadhesive properties of polymers [58].

Fig. 2. X-ray patterns of A) chitosan and B) thiol-functionalized chitosan (CsSH).

The thermal stability was studied by thermogravimetry and the thermograms of pure chitosan and thiol-grafted chitosan are shown in Fig. 3. According to the measurements, weight loss of chitosan took place in two stages. The first thermal event was observed up to 146°C , which was assigned to the release of sorbed water. The second stage started near 230°C and corresponded to the decomposition of the chitosan main chain [40,63,64]. Compared to chitosan, for the thiolated derivative the degradation of the

backbone started significantly earlier, indicating that the presence of the thiol groups grafted to the polymer main chain decreased the degradation resistance of the polysaccharide. These results were in agreement with reported literature, where substituted polymers usually show lower thermal stability due to the disruption of the ordered structure of the neat polymer by the grafted molecule [40,65]. After a progressive loss of water up to 135 °C, which depends on the initial moisture content of the samples [66], the modified polymer decomposition reaction was observed to start at 180 °C. The incorporation of thiol groups decreased the temperature of the maximum decomposition rate and, at the same time, a small shoulder appeared indicating two-stage decomposition pattern in the case of the modified chitosan, in contrast to the single peak registered for the pure chitosan, which could be an indicative of the incorporation of a new compound into the polymer main chain [65], verifying the successful functionalization of Cs.

Fig. 3. TGA (left axis) and dTGA (right axis) curves of chitosan (solid line) and thiolated chitosan (dash line) under inert atmosphere.

3.2. Characterization of CsSH/BMI hydrogels

It has been shown that maleimides could act as Michael acceptors for primary amine donors [23], but maleimide reacts approximately 1000 times faster with thiols than with

amines at neutral pH and below [26]. Hydrogels with 1:2 to 1:3 thiol-to-maleimide equivalent ratios were successfully synthesized and characterized in order to evaluate the effect of the cross-linker amount.

Oscillatory rheology measurements were performed to evaluate the evolution of the rheological parameters during the *in situ* gelation of CsSH/BMI hydrogels (Fig. 4A). The point where the storage (G') and the loss (G'') moduli crossover is traditionally assumed to reflect the transition from liquid-like to solid-like behaviour, namely, the gel point [10]. In accordance with the results presented by other authors [1,27,28,67,68], very fast gelation times could be observed for both compositions. A further increase in the cross-linker amount from 1:2 to 1:3 resulted in longer gelation time, which could be related to possible steric impediments and/or dilution effects due to the presence of long bismaleimide chains involved in the reaction. The initial mixing of both precursors and the proper conditions of the reaction itself made the cross-point in CsSH/BMI 1:2 not observable, but it could be intuited by the trend of the moduli. In the case of CsSH/BMI 1:3 the gel point happened after 95 s, and, as it could be appreciated, after an adequate handling of the precursors, the final materials presented the desirable property of being formed *in situ* which is essential for injectable hydrogels.

Fig. 4. A) Dynamic moduli (G' (filled symbols) and G'' (empty symbols)) as a function of time for ■ CsSH/BMI 1:2 and ▲ CsSH/BMI 1:3 at 37 °C and B) Frequency sweep of 'click' cross-linked hydrogels at 37 °C.

Dynamic rheological analysis was also performed to study the final viscoelastic properties of the different as-prepared hydrogels at 37 °C (Fig. 4B). As it could be observed, samples showed the desirable solid-like gel behaviour, presenting permanent elastic character in the studied frequency range, where G' was maintained constant and always higher than G'' . The mean G' , G'' and damping factor ($\tan \delta$) values for both hydrogels are shown in Table 2. The value of the damping factor represents the overall viscoelasticity of the polymer, and was less than 1 in both systems, which was an indicative of predominantly elastic over the viscous behaviour. Therefore, the polymeric network was considered to be strongly cross-linked, being slightly more noticeable in the case of CsSH/BMI 1:3 indicating greater amount of effective intermolecular cross-links as suggested in literature [34,69]. Besides, for the values obtained for the storage moduli were in accordance with those previously reported by other authors for different chitosan-based hydrogels cross-linked via Michael addition [67,70].

Table 2

Mean storage and loss modulus and $\tan \delta$ values of cross-linked hydrogels at 37 °C (average \pm standard deviation, $n = 3$).

Hydrogel samples	G' (Pa)	G'' (Pa)	$\tan \delta$ (G''/G')
CsSH/BMI 1:2	974.6 \pm 105.6	452.3 \pm 128.2	0.464 \pm 0.056
CsSH/BMI 1:3	3331.5 \pm 502.4	1206.5 \pm 388.4	0.361 \pm 0.021

The architecture of the final polymeric network in hydrogels is obviously extremely important in biomedical applications as drug delivery or tissue engineering. With the aim of deepen in it, the average mesh size (ξ , nm), the cross-linking density (n_e , mol/m³) and the average molecular weight of the polymeric chain between

neighbouring cross-links (M_c , kg/mol), were calculated based on the so-called rubber elastic theory (RET) from Equation (5), (6) and (7), respectively [71], to evaluate the effects of BMI concentration on the ultrastructure of the hydrogels.

$$\xi = \left(\frac{G' \cdot N_A}{RT} \right)^{-1/3} \quad (5)$$

$$n_e = \frac{G_e}{RT} \quad (6)$$

$$M_c = \frac{c\rho RT}{G_e} \quad (7)$$

where G' is the storage modulus, N_A is the Avogadro's constant (6.022×10^{23}), R is the gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J/K}\cdot\text{mol}$), T is the temperature (310 K), G_e represents the plateau value of storage modulus measured by frequency sweep test, c is the polymer concentration in the samples (7 \%w/v) and ρ is the density of water at 310 K (993 kg/m^3).

The calculated structural parameters for CsSH/BMI hydrogels are summarized in Table 3. It was found that hydrogels displayed a mesh size (ξ) of 7.61 and 5.12 nm for CsSH/BMI 1:2 and CsSH/BMI 1:3, respectively, resulting in interesting biological scaffolds which could allow the transport of small molecules through the network [72]. The resulting values for the cross-linking density (n_e) suggested a higher cross-linked network for the hydrogel containing a higher amount of cross-linker, increasing from 0.38 to 1.29 mol/m^3 [73]. Finally, the average molecular weight between neighbouring cross-link points took values of 184.28 and 57.47 kg/mol for CsSH/BMI 1:2 and CsSH/BMI 1:3, respectively. M_c results were in accordance with those obtained by Karvinen et al. for cross-linked polysaccharide-based hydrogels [71], even if they

observed lower values for n_e . As it can be observed, ξ and M_c values decreased and n_e values increased when the amount of BMI in the hydrogel increased, namely, the results were in line with the expected behaviour that the higher the G' , the lower the mesh size and M_c , and higher the cross-linking density [71], highlighting the great cross-linking efficiency and the potentiality of the developed thiol-maleimide system.

Table 3

Parameters of chitosan-based cross-linked hydrogels determined based on the rheological frequency sweep analysis (average \pm standard deviation, $n = 3$).

Hydrogel samples	ξ (nm)	n_e (mol/m ³)	M_c (kg/mol)
CsSH/BMI 1:2	7.61 \pm 0.18	0.38 \pm 0.03	184.28 \pm 12.99
CsSH/BMI 1:3	5.12 \pm 0.62	1.29 \pm 0.46	57.47 \pm 20.62

The porous microstructure of hydrogels is also crucial concerning materials for tissue engineering [74] and, thus, it was studied by scanning electron microscopy (Fig. 5). As it can be observed, the internal morphology of the hydrogels seemed to be affected by the composition, specifically by the amount of cross-linker in the samples. Even if porous microstructures were obtained with both compositions, differences in the networks were apparent. While CsSH/BMI 1:2 presented pores homogeneously distributed (318 \pm 98 μ m), increasing the BMI amount to 1:3 ratio led to heterogeneous microstructure with less sum of bigger pores (343 \pm 124 μ m) in combination with smaller pores (56 \pm 25 μ m). Indeed, the use of greater amounts of cross-linking agent in the formulations is normally related with a decrease in the pore size due to higher cross-linking densities [34] and these findings are in agreement with the above results obtained for the viscoelastic behaviour and structural parameters of CsSH/BMI networks.

Fig. 5. SEM images of the freeze-dried hydrogels: A) CsSH/BMI 1:2 and B) CsSH/BMI 1:3.

When dealing with cross-linked hydrogels, the study of their swelling properties in different media is particularly relevant. Concerning chitosan-based hydrogels, the swelling ratio would be highly related to the cross-linking degree, the microstructure and the pH-sensitivity derived from the cationic character of the polysaccharide [35,37,75]. In order to evaluate the responsive capacity of the as-prepared hydrogels, the swelling behaviour was studied at 37 °C in PBS (pH = 7.4) and HCl (pH = 1). The swelling kinetics and the equilibrium swelling values after 48 h in both media for the two CsSH/BMI hydrogels are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Swelling kinetics at 37 °C for ■ CsSH/BMI 1:2 and ▲ CsSH/BMI 1:3 in A) PBS and B) HCl, and C) equilibrium swelling ratio at 37 °C after 48 h.

As expected, the swelling capacity of the hydrogels was found to be highly sensitive to the surrounding pH being notably higher the swelling degree in acidic medium as a result of the repulsive forces between the chitosan chains between the protonated remaining amino groups in the chitosan backbone [35].

As Tang et al. corroborated, the equilibrium properties, the viscoelastic modulus and the maximum swelling ratio could be controlled by varying the dosage of cross-linker [76]. Besides, the swelling degree is normally assumed to decrease with increasing cross-linking degree [35]. Thus, with the addition of the bifunctional cross-linker in a 1:3 ratio the subsequent decrease in the swelling ratio of the hydrogel was expected with respect to that measured for the 1:2 ratio. The results were in agreement with the statements and CsSH/BMI 1:3 hydrogel presented lower swelling ratios in both media, implying a more cross-linked network, following the same trend of the rheological

behaviour and confirming the relation between the 3D microstructure and the swelling conduct [75].

With the aim of better understand the results, the swelling kinetics of hydrogels was adjusted to the Eq. (8) reported in the literature [37].

$$\frac{t}{SR} = \frac{1}{SR_{max}^2 \cdot k_s} + \frac{1}{SR_{max}} \cdot t \quad (8)$$

where SR is the swelling degree at time t, SR_{max} the maximum swelling value and k_s the swelling constant rate. The obtained adjustment parameters are presented in Table 4. The swelling process followed in both cases first order kinetics with correlation coefficients above 0.99.

Regarding the effect of the pH, as shown, the absorption and retention capability of the hydrogels was notably higher in acidic medium, as already mentioned. Furthermore, under acidic pH, the SR_{max} values were considerably higher than the SR at 2h, whereas in physiological solution both values were closer. These results confirmed the difference between the two hydrogel formulations when reaching the equilibrium. Namely, both hydrogels reached the equilibrium after 2 h of incubation in PBS and nevertheless, it took them more time in acidic medium (24 h). Moreover, when using acidic pH as the swelling medium, the value of k_s was much lower, since the amount of solution absorbed by the hydrogels was higher in this media and the equilibrium swelling slower, making the swelling rate quite low. By comparing the two hydrogels, CsSH/BMI 1:3 presented lower swelling rates, i.e. higher constant values, corroborating the influence of the cross-linking density on the swelling kinetics.

Table 4
Swelling parameters of chitosan-based cross-linked hydrogels at 37 °C in different aqueous media.

SR _{max} (%)	SR _{2h} (%)	k _s · 10 ⁴ (g _{hydrogel} / g _{solution} · s)
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PBS			
CsSH/BMI 1:2	3392	3263	0.113
CsSH/BMI 1:3	2430	2554	0.847
HCl (0.1 M)			
CsSH/BMI 1:2	18564	6640	0.011
CsSH/BMI 1:3	15834	13280	0.079

Furthermore, one of the most important characteristics of the chitosan is its ability to degrade by the attack of several enzymes as chitosanases and lysozymes, which promote the disruption of the glycosylation reactions in addition to hydrolysis. These enzymes are present in tears and saliva where they act as a barrier against infections. Thus, in order to mimic the *in vivo* degradation process of CsSH/BMI hydrogels, lysozymes were added to the medium following the procedure reported in our previous work [35]. Thus, the biodegradability of the synthesized hydrogels was assessed by incubating the samples in PBS and lysozyme/PBS for long periods and the registered mass loss was correlated to the hydrolytic and enzymatic degradation of the material, respectively (Fig. 7). As it could be observed, the degradation of the hydrogels was slightly sensitive to the cross-linking density and, in a higher extent, to the presence of lysozyme in the medium. Indeed, the presence of specific enzymes not only accelerated the degradation process of the cross-linked hydrogels but also provoked the complete dissolution of the material. Namely, hydrogels were completely degraded after 24 hours in lysozyme containing solution, whereas in lysozyme free PBS the hydrogels remained stable after the initial mass loss during the first two days of incubation.

Fig. 7. Dry weight remaining ratio of ■ CsSH/BMI 1:2 and ▲ CsSH/BMI 1:3 in 1 mg/mL lysozyme/PBS (filled symbols) and in PBS without lysozyme (empty symbols) at 37 °C as a function of time.

Moreover, the CsSH:BMI ratio was also a determining parameter when studying the degradation of hydrogels. When comparing the lysozyme free hydrolytic degradation, the CsSH/BMI 1:3 hydrogel presented slightly higher degradation degrees, which could be related to the higher content of hydrolysable BMI cross-linker in the sample. On the contrary, in enzymes containing environment, the resulting degradation curves were inverted and the less cross-linked hydrogel degraded slightly faster, suggesting that the different degradation mechanism that involved the enzymes actuation was affected by the cross-linking density. One of the several requirements that need to satisfy the hydrogels that will be implanted inside the human body and thus, for being useful for biomedical design, should be the biodegradability. This behaviour will create space for cell growth and rearrangement, and for the newly formed tissues in the case of tissue engineering or will assist the release of drugs across the hydrogel on drug delivery applications [77].

4. Conclusions

A water-soluble chitosan derivative was successfully synthesized after the thiolation of the original polymer with thiolactic acid, which resulted highly efficient for the

subsequent formation of biopolymer based-hydrogels. Thus, 3D porous networks were obtained through thiol-maleimide coupling under mild physiological conditions. For the sake of improvement, the amount of cross-linker was increased when forming the hydrogels, achieving materials with highly enhanced properties. Thereby, increasing the amount of bismaleimide in the hydrogels notably improved the storage modulus value, which might be related with an increase in effective cross-linking density and simultaneous decrease in average molecular weight between cross-linking points. In parallel with this observation, the swelling degree values were smaller when increasing the amount of cross-linker, supporting the previous hypothesis. Besides, lysozymes was observed to act on the polymeric networks, which notably accelerated the degradation of the hydrogels, giving an idea of the response of the as-prepared materials under human body conditions.

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REFERENCES

- [1] E.A. Phelps, N.O. Enemchukwu, V.F. Fiore, J.C. Sy, N. Murthy, T.A. Sulchek, T.H. Barker, A.J. García, Maleimide cross-linked bioactive PEG hydrogel exhibits improved

reaction kinetics and cross-linking for cell encapsulation and in situ delivery, *Adv. Mater.* 24(1) (2012) 64–70. doi: 10.1002/adma.201103574.

[2] J.A. Yang, J. Yeom, B.W. Hwang, A.S. Hoffman, S.K. Hahn, In situ-forming injectable hydrogels for regenerative medicine, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 39(12) (2014) 1973–1986. doi: 10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2014.07.006.

[3] B.V. Slaughter, S.S. Khurshid, O.Z. Fisher, A. Khademhosseini, N.A. Peppas, Hydrogels in regenerative medicine, *Adv. Mater.* 21(0) (2009) 3307–3329. doi: 10.1002/adma.200802106.

[4] M. Annaka, K. Mortensen, M.E. Vigild, T. Matsuura, S. Tsuji, T. Ueda, H. Tsujinaka, Design of an injectable in situ gelation biomaterials for vitreous substitute, *Biomacromolecules* 12 (2011) 4011–4021. doi: 10.1021/bm201012f.

[5] M. Śmiga–Matuszowicz, A. Korytkowska–Walach, B. Nowak, R. Pilawka, M. Lesiak, A.L. Sieroń, Poly(isosorbide succinate) –based in situ forming implants as potential systems for local drug delivery: Preliminary studies, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 91 (2018) 311–317. doi: 10.1016/j.msec.2018.05.046.

[6] A.E. Rydholm, C.N. Bowman, K.S. Anseth, Degradable thiol–acrylate photopolymers: polymerization and degradation behavior of an in situ forming biomaterial, *Biomaterials* 26(22) (2005) 4495–4606. doi: 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2004.11.046.

[7] B. Balakrishnan, A. Jayakrishnan, Self-cross-linking biopolymers as injectable in situ forming biodegradable scaffolds, *Biomaterials* 26(18) (2005) 3941–3951. doi: 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2004.10.005.

[8] H. Tan, C.R. Chu, K.A. Payne, K.G. Marra, Injectable in situ forming biodegradable chitosan–hyaluronic acid based hydrogels for cartilage tissue engineering, *Biomaterials* 30(13) (2009) 2499–2506. doi: 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2008.12.080.

- [9] B. Balakrishnan, M. Mohanty, P.R. Umashankar, A. Jayakrishnan, Evaluation of an in situ forming hydrogel wound dressing based on oxidized alginate and gelatin, *Biomaterials* 26(32) (2005) 6335–6342. doi: 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2005.04.012.
- [10] Z.Q. Liu, Z. Wei, X.L. Zhu, G.Y. Huang, F. Xu, J.H. Yang, Y. Osada, M. Zrínyi, J.H. Li, Y.M. Chen, Dextran–based hydrogel formed by thiol–Michael addition reaction for 3D cell encapsulation, *Colloids Surf., B: Biointerfaces* 128 (2015) 140–148. doi: 10.1016/j.colsurfb.2015.02.005.
- [11] N.G. Moon, A.M. Pekkanen, T.E. Long, T.N. Showalter, B. Libby, Thiol–Michael ‘click’ hydrogels as an imageable packing material for cancer therapy, *Polymer* 125 (2017) 66–75. doi: 10.1016/j.polymer.2017.07.078.
- [12] M.F. Sonnenschein, J.B. Werness, K.A. Patankar, X. Jin, M.Z. Larive, From rigid and flexible foams to elastomers via Michael addition chemistry, *Polymer* 106 (2016) 128–139. doi: 10.1016/j.polymer.2016.10.054.
- [13] R. Fu, G.D. Fu, Polymeric nanomaterials from combined click chemistry and controlled radical polymerization, *Polym. Chem.* 2 (2011) 465–475. doi: 10.1039/C0PY00174K.
- [14] Z. Wang, Z. Dai, J. Wu, N. Zhao, J. Xu, Vacuum–dried robust bridged silsesquioxane aerogels, *Adv. Mater.* 25 (2013) 4494–4497. doi: 10.1002/adma.201301617.
- [15] S. Chatani, R.J. Sheridan, M. Podgorski, D.P. Nair, C.N. Bowman, Temporal control of thiol–click chemistry, *Chem. Mater.* 25 (2013) 3897–3901. doi: 10.1021/cm402229j.
- [16] D.P. Nair, M. Podgórski, S. Chatani, T. Gong, W. Xi, C.R. Fenoli, C.N. Bowman, The thiol–Michael addition click reaction: a powerful and widely used tool in materials chemistry, *Chem. Mater.* 26 (2014) 724–744. doi: 10.1021/cm402180t.

- [17] H. Lin, J. Ou, Z. Liu, H. Wang, J. Dong, H. Zou, Facile construction of macroporous hybrid monoliths *via* thiol–methacrylate Michael addition click reaction for capillary liquid chromatography, *J. Chromatogr. A* (2015) 1379, 34–42. doi: 10.1016/j.chroma.2014.12.031.
- [18] E. Çakmakçi, B. Yuce–Dursun, S. Demir, Maleic anhydride functionalization of OSTE based coatings *via* thiol–ene ‘Click’ reaction for the covalent immobilization of xylanase, *React. Funct. Polym.* 111 (2017) 38–43. doi: 10.1016/j.reactfunctpolym.2016.11.006.
- [19] A.P.P. Kröger, R.J.E.A. Boonen, J.M.J. Paulusse, Well–defined single–chain polymer nanoparticles *via* thiol–Michael addition, *Polymer* 120 (2017) 119–128. doi: 10.1016/j.polymer.2017.05.040.
- [20] G.N. Grover, S.N.S. Alconcel, N.M. Matsumoto, H.D. Maynard, Trapping of thiol–terminated acrylate polymers with divinyl sulfone to generate well–defined semitelechelic Michael acceptor polymers, *Macromolecules* 42(20) (2009) 7657–7663. doi: 10.1021/ma901036x.
- [21] B.D. Mather, K. Viswanathan, K.M. Miller, T.E. Long, Michael addition reactions in macromolecular design for emerging technologies, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 31 (2006) 487–531. doi: 10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2006.03.001.
- [22] R.M. Stolz, B.H. Northrop, Experimental and theoretical studies of selective thiol–ene and thiol–yne click reactions involving N–substituted maleimides, *J. Org. Chem.* 78 (2013) 8105–8116. doi: 10.1021/jo4014436.
- [23] A.D. Baldwin, K.L. Kiick, Tunable degradation of maleimide–thiol adducts in reducing environments, *Bioconjugate Chem.* 22 (2011) 1946–1953. doi: 10.1021/bc200148v.

- [24] M. Arslan, T.N. Gevrek, A. Sanyal, R. Sanyal, Cyclodextrin mediated polymer coupling via thiol–maleimide conjugation: facile access to functionalizable hydrogels, *RSC Adv.* 4 (2014) 57834–57841. doi: 10.1039/C4RA12408A.
- [25] S. Belbekhouche, M. Guerrouache, B. Carbonnier, Thiol–maleimide Michael addition click reaction: a new route to surface modification of porous polymeric monolith, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* 217 (2016) 997–1006. doi: 10.1002/macp.201500427.
- [26] S. Ravi, V.R. Krishnamurthy, J.M. Caves, C.A. Haller, E.L. Chaikof, Maleimide–thiol coupling of a bioactive peptide to an elastin–like protein polymer, *Acta Biomater.* 8 (2012) 627–635. doi: 10.1016/j.actbio.2011.10.027.
- [27] L.E. Jansen, L.J. Negrón–Piñeiro, S. Galarza, S.R. Peyton, Control of thiol–maleimide reaction kinetics in PEG hydrogel networks, *Acta Biomater.* 70 (2018) 120–128. doi: 10.1016/j.actbio.2018.01.043.
- [28] N.J. Darling, Y–S. Hung, S. Sharma, T. Segura, Controlling the kinetics of thiol–maleimide Michael–type addition gelation kinetics for the generation of homogeneous poly(ethylene glycol) hydrogels, *Biomaterials* 101 (2016) 199–206. doi: 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2016.05.053.
- [29] Y. Shtenberg, M. Goldfeder, A. Schroeder, H. Bianco–Peled, Alginate modified with maleimide–terminated PEG as drug carriers with enhanced mucoadhesion, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 175 (2017) 337–346. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2017.07.076.
- [30] P. Buono, A. Duval, L. Averous, Y. Habibi, Lignin–based materials through thiol–maleimide ‘click’ polymerization, *ChemSusChem* 10 (2017) 984–992. doi: 10.1002/cssc.201601738.

- [31] L. Billiet, O. Gok, A.P. Dove, A. Sanyal, L–T.T. Nguyen, F.E. Du Prez, Metal–free functionalization of linear polyurethanes by thiol–maleimide coupling reactions, *Macromolecules* 44 (2011) 7874–7878. doi: 10.1021/ma201323g.
- [32] C. García–Astrain, I. Algar, A. Gandini, A. Eceiza, M.A. Corcuera, N. Gabilondo, Hydrogel synthesis by aqueous Diels–Alder reaction between furan modified methacrylate and polyetheramine–based bismaleimides, *J. Polym. Sci. A* 53 (2015) 699–708. doi: 10.1002/pola.27495.
- [33] C. García–Astrain, A. Gandini, C. Peña, I. Algar, A. Eceiza, M.A. Corcuera, N. Gabilondo, Diels–Alder ‘click’ chemistry for the cross–linking of furfuryl–gelatin–polyetheramine hydrogels, *RSC Adv.* 4 (2014) 35578–35587. doi: 10.1039/C4RA06122E.
- [34] K. González, C. García–Astrain, A. Santamaria–Echart, L. Ugarte, L. Avérous, A. Eceiza, N. Gabilondo, Starch/graphene hydrogels via click chemistry with relevant electrical and antibacterial properties, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 202 (2018) 372–381. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2018.09.007.
- [35] O. Guaresti, C. García–Astrain, R.H. Aguirresarobe, A. Eceiza, N. Gabilondo, Synthesis of stimuli–responsive chitosan–based hydrogels by Diels–Alder cross–linking ‘click’ reaction as potential carriers for drug administration, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 183 (2018) 278–286. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2017.12.034.
- [36] G. Ma, X. Zhang, J. Han, G. Song, J. Nie, Photo–polymerizable chitosan derivative prepared by Michael reaction of chitosan and polyethylene glycol diacrylate (PEGDA), *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 45 (2009) 499–503. doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2009.08.007.
- [37] O. Guaresti, C. García–Astrain, T. Palomares, A. Alonso–Varona, A. Eceiza, N. Gabilondo, Synthesis and characterization of a biocompatible chitosan–based

hydrogel cross-linked via 'click' chemistry for controlled drug release, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 102 (2017) 1–9. doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2017.04.003.

[38] H. Zhang, A. Qadeer, W. Chen, In situ gelable interpenetrating double network hydrogel formulated from binary components: thiolated chitosan and oxidized dextran, *Biomacromolecules* 12(5) (2011) 1428–1437. doi: 10.1021/bm101192b.

[39] A. Anitha, N. Deepa, K.P. Chennazhi, S.V. Nair, H. Tamura, R. Jayakumar, Development of mucoadhesive thiolated chitosan nanoparticles for biomedical applications, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 83(1) (2011) 66–73. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2010.07.028.

[40] M. Jiang, K. Wang, J.F. Kennedy, J. Nie, Q. Yu, G. Ma, Preparation and characterization of water-soluble chitosan derivative by Michael addition reaction, *Inter. J. Biol. Macromol.* 47(5) (2010) 696–699. doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2010.09.002.

[41] A.M. Abdelgawad, M.E. El-Naggar, S.M. Hudson, O.J. Rojas, Fabrication and characterization of bactericidal thiol-chitosan and chitosan iodoacetamide nanofibers. *Inter. J. Biol. Macromol.* 94 (2017) 96–105. doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2016.07.061.

[42] X. Zhu, X., M. Su, S. Tang, L. Wang, X. Liang, F. Meng, Y. Hong, Z. Xu, Synthesis of thiolated chitosan and preparation nanoparticles with sodium alginate for ocular drug delivery, *Mol. Vis.* 18 (2012) 1973–1982. PMID: PMC3413446.

[43] S. Dünnhaupt, J. Barthelmes, C.C. Thurner, C. Waldner, D. Sakloetsakun, A. Bernkop-Schnürch, S-protected thiolated chitosan: Synthesis and in vitro characterization. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 90(2) (2012) 765–772. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2012.05.028.

[44] R. Jayakumar, R.L. Reis, J.F. Mano, Synthesis and characterization of pH-sensitive thiol-containing chitosan beads for controlled drug delivery applications. *Drug Deliv.* 14 (2007) 9–17. doi: 10.1080/10717540600739872.

- [45] B. Han, Y. Wei, X. Jia, J. Xu, G. Li, Correlation of the structure, properties, and antimicrobial activity of a soluble thiolated chitosan derivative, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 125 (2012) 143–148. doi: 10.1002/app.36548.
- [46] K. Maculotti, I. Genta, P. Perugini, M. Imam, A. Bernkop–Schnürch, F. Pavanetto, Preparation and in vitro evaluation of thiolated chitosan microparticles, *J. Microencapsul.* 22(5) (2005) 459–470. doi: 10.1080/02652040500162220.
- [47] Y. Shitrit, H. Bianco–Peled, Acrylated chitosan for mucoadhesive drug delivery systems, *Int. J. Pharm.* 517 (2017) 247–255. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2016.12.023.
- [48] A. Bernkop–Schnürch, Thiomers: A new generation of mucoadhesive polymers, *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 57(11) (2005) 1569–1582. doi: 10.1016/j.addr.2005.07.002.
- [49] A. Bernkop–Schnürch, M. Hornof, D. Guggi, Thiolated chitosans, *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 57 (2004) 9–17. PMID: 14729077.
- [50] A. Mahmood, M. Lanthaler, F. Laffleur, C.W. Huck, A. Bernkop–Schnürch, Thiolated chitosan micelles: Highly mucoadhesive drug carriers, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 167 (2017) 250–258. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2017.03.019.
- [51] B.M. Chesnutt, A.M. Viano, Y. Yuan, Y. Yang, T. Guda, M.R. Appleford, J.L. Ong, W.O. Haggard, J.D. Bumgardner, Design and characterization of a novel chitosan/nanocrystalline calcium phosphate composite scaffold for bone regeneration, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. A* 88(2) (2009) 491–502. doi: 10.1002/jbm.a.31878.
- [52] F.G.L. Medeiros Borsagli, I.C. Carvalho, H.S. Mansur, Amino acid–grafted and *N*-acetylated chitosan thiomers: Construction of 3D bio–scaffolds for potential cartilage repair applications, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 114 (2018) 270–282. doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2018.03.133.
- [53] A.I. Ruiz Matute, A. Cardelle–Cobas, A.B. García–Bermejo, A. Montilla, A. Olano, N. Corzo, Synthesis, characterization and functional properties of galactosylated

derivatives of chitosan through amide formation, *Food Hydrocoll.* 33(2) (2013) 245–255. doi: 10.1016/j.foodhyd.2013.03.016.

[54] N. Ahmed Mohamed, M. Mohamed Fahmy, Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some novel cross-linked chitosan hydrogels, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 13(9) (2012) 1119–11209. doi: 10.3390/ijms130911194.

[55] J. Zhang, W. Tan, Z. Zhang, Y. Song, Q. Li, F. Dong, Z. Guo, Synthesis, characterization, and the antifungal activity of chitosan derivatives containing urea groups, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 109 (2018) 1061–1067. doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2017.11.092.

[56] C. Radhakumary, M. Antonty, K. Sreenivasan, Drug loaded thermoresponsive and cytocompatible chitosan based hydrogel as a potential wound dressing, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 83(2) (2011) 705–713. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2010.08.042.

[57] J.C. Santos, P.M. Moreno, A.A. Mansur, V. Leiro, H.S. Mansur, A.P. Pêgo, Functionalized chitosan derivatives as nonviral vectors: physicochemical properties of acylated N,N,N-trimethyl chitosan/oligonucleotide nanopolyplexes, *Soft Matter* 11(41) (2015) 8113–8125. doi: 10.1039/c5sm01403d.

[58] M. Prabakaran, S. Gong, Novel thiolated carboxymethyl chitosan- β -cyclodextrin as mucoadhesive hydrophobic drug delivery carriers, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 73(1) (2008) 117–125. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2007.11.005.

[59] Y. Li, J. Xu, Y. Xu, L. Huang, J. Wang, X. Cheng, Synthesis and characterization of fluorescent chitosan-ZnSe/ZnS nanoparticles for potential drug carriers, *RSC Adv.* 5 (2015) 38810–38817. doi: 10.1039/C5RA02933C.

[60] S. Kumar, J. Koh, Physicochemical, optical and biological activity of chitosan-chromone derivative for biomedical applications, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 13 (2012) 6102–6116. doi: 10.3390/ijms13056102.

- [61] M. Arteché Pujana, L. Pérez-Álvarez, L.C. Cesteros Iturbe, I. Katime, pH-sensitive chitosan-folate nanogels crosslinked with biocompatible dicarboxylic acids, *Eur. Polym. J.* 61 (2014) 215–225. doi: 10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2014.10.007.
- [62] J.S. Boateng, D. Areago, Composite sodium alginate and chitosan based wafers for buccal delivery of macromolecules, *J. Anal. Pharm. Chem.* 1(5) (2014) 1022–1028. ISSN: 2381-8913.
- [63] F. Stuaní Pereira, D. L. da Silva Agostini, A.E. Job, E.R. Pérez González, Thermal studies of chitin-chitosan derivatives, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* (2013) 114(1), 321–327. doi: 10.1007/s10973-012-2835-z.
- [64] C.G.T. Neto, J.A. Giacometti, A.E. Job, F.C. Ferreira, J.L.C. Fonseca, M.R. Pereira, Thermal analysis of chitosan based networks, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 62(2), (2005) 97–103. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2005.02.022.
- [65] S. Nanaki, M. Tseklima, E. Christodoulou, K. Triantafyllidis, M. Kostoglou, D.N. Bikiaris, Thiolated chitosan masked polymeric microspheres with incorporated mesocellular silica foam (MCF) for intranasal delivery of Paliperidone, *Polymers* 9(11) (2017) 617–638. doi: 10.3390/polym9110617.
- [66] I. Olivas-Armendáriz, E. Santos-Rodríguez, S. Correa-Espinoza, D-S. Domínguez-Domínguez, I. Márquez-Méndez, M. Mendoza-Duarte, M-C, Chavarría-Gaytán, S-A Martel-Estrada, Evaluation of mechanical and thermophysical properties of chitosan/poly(DL-lactide-co-glycolide)/multiwalled carbon nanotubes for tissue engineering, *Am. J. Mater. Sci.* 5(1) (2015) 9–16. doi: 10.5923/j.materials.20150501.02.
- [67] M-S. Kim, Y-J. Choi, I. Noh, G. Tae, Synthesis and characterization of *in situ* chitosan-based hydrogel via grafting of carboxyethyl acrylate, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. A* 83(3) (2007) 674–682. doi: 10.1002/jbm.a.31278.

- [68] J. Qu, X. Zhao, P.X. Ma, B. Guo, pH-responsive self-healing injectable hydrogel based on N-carboxyethyl chitosan for hepatocellular carcinoma therapy, *Acta Biomater.* 58 (2017) 168–180. doi: 10.1016/j.actbio.2017.06.001.
- [69] D. Teng, Z. Wu, X. Zhang, Y. Wang, C. Zheng, Z. Wang, C. Li, Synthesis and characterization of in situ cross-linked hydrogel based on self-assembly of thiol-modified chitosan with PEG diacrylate using Michael type addition, *Polymer* 51(3) (2010) 639–646. doi: 10.1016/j.polymer.2009.12.003.
- [70] Y. Yu, C. Deng, F. Meng, Q. Shi, J. Feijen, Z. Zhong, Novel injectable biodegradable glycol chitosan-based hydrogels crosslinked by Michael-type addition reaction with oligo(acryloyl carbonate)-*b*-poly(ethylene glycol)-*b*-oligo(acryloyl carbonate) copolymers, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. A* 99(2) (2011) 316–326. doi: 10.1002/jbm.a.33199.
- [71] J. Karvinen, T.O. Ihalainen, M.T. Calejo, I. Jönkkäri, M. Kellomäki, Characterization of the microstructure of hydrazine crosslinked polysaccharide-based hydrogels through rheological and diffusion studies, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 94 (2019) 1056–1066. doi: 10.1016/j.msec.2018.10.048.
- [72] J. Li, D.J. Mooney, Designing hydrogels for controlled drug delivery, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* 1 (2016) 1–17. doi: 10.1038/natrevmats.2016.71.
- [73] C. García-Astrain, K. González, T. Gurrea, O. Guaresti, I. Algar, A. Eceiza, N. Gabilondo, Maleimide-grafted cellulose nanocrystals as cross-linkers for bionanocomposite hydrogels, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 149 (2016) 94–101. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2016.04.091.
- [74] S. Fernandes-Silva, J. Moreira-Silva, T.H. Silva, R.L. Perez-Martin, C.G. Sotelo, J.F. Mano, A.R.C. Duarte, R.L. Reis, Porous hydrogels from shark skin collagen

crosslinked under dense carbon dioxide atmosphere, *Macromol. Biosci.* 13 (2013) 1621–1631. doi: 10.1002/mabi.201300228.

[75] O. Guaresti, C. García–Astrain, L. Urbina, A. Eceiza, N. Gabilondo, Reversible swelling behaviour of Diels–Alder clicked chitosan hydrogels in response to pH changes, *eXPRESS Polym. Lett.* 13 (2019) 27–36. doi: 10.3144/expresspolymlett.2019.4.

[76] S. Tang, B.D. Olsen, Controlling topological entanglement in engineered protein hydrogels with a variety of thiol coupling chemistries, *Front. Chem.* 2 (2014) 23–33. doi: 10.3389/fchem.2014.00023.

[77] Y. Li, J. Rodrigues, H. Tomás, Injectable and biodegradable hydrogels: gelation, biodegradation and biomedical applications, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 41 (2012) 2193–2221. doi: 10.1039/c1cs15203c.